

Cation substitution in all solution-processed $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Cd,Zn})\text{SnS}_4$ superstrate solar cells

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Abstract

Thin-film solar cells constituted of abundant elements are the key to ensuring mass production, reducing energy costs, and meeting energy demands. Kesterite, is a cost-effective light absorber, however showed low compatibility with a superstrate architecture, and has been studied mostly with the costly substrate. We demonstrate that a cation substitution of Zn by Cd improves the absorber compatibility on a superstrate architecture. Moreover, we employed all solution-processed using water and ethanol mixture as green solvents for thin-film deposition. An increase of the Cd amount in the absorber layer gave improved crystallinity and crystal size increment, band gap decrement, and a change in crystal structure from kesterite to cernyite. The composition of the buffer layer is controlled by the diffusion of Zn into CdS, forming $(\text{Cd,Zn})\text{S}$ with a relative Cd–Zn ratio. Solar cells prepared with high Cd showed a thicker depletion width and a reduction in the defect carrier density, leading to a significant increment in the power conversion efficiency up to 1.9%. Furthermore, the fabricated solar cells show high stability on continuous light illumination of over 80 hours. The investigation of the electrical losses in $\text{Cu}_2\text{CdSnS}_4$ suggests ample opportunity to improve the solar cell performance in a superstrate architecture.

Keywords: Spray pyrolysis; Kesterite; Stannite; Superstrate solar cells; Thin-film photovoltaics.

1. Introduction

The unparalleled growth in the photovoltaic (PV) market, mainly relies on wafer-based silicon technology, however, this can comprise future challenges in terms of material availability and production. Alternatively, thin-film PV is of significant interest since they have a high potential to meet the increasing energy demand.^[1] Thin-film PV technologies have advantages in the manufacturing processes, offering fast deposition processes for large-scale PV production, less usage of raw elements, and low energy paybacks and carbon footprint.^[2] Furthermore, they provide aesthetics in applications where lightweight, flexible, or semitransparency is required. These advantages are of special interest on the emerging energy applications, such as long-term powering of outdoors and indoors sensors, the internet of things, building integration PV, or small decentralized installations for self-consumption.^[3]

Thin-film PV technologies depend on strategic materials with relatively low abundance such as Te in CdTe, or In, Ga, and Se in the case of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS), which raises doubt for their gigawatt-scale production.^[4] It is of paramount interest, to find suitable substitutes for these raw materials with more abundant elements. Emerging chalcogenide materials with competitive PV properties have received attention in the last decades, as possible candidates to substitute the critical elements. In particular Cu₂ZnSn(S,Se)₄ (CZTS) received special attention, due to its composition made of abundant elements, and PV performances, such as close to ideal direct band-gap, p-type conductivity, and a moderate temperature crystallization of 500 – 600 °C.^[5] The composition CZTS thin films are compatible with various wet-chemistry processing methods, allowing them to be easily implemented in cost-effective roll-to-roll processes with high throughput. In particular, spray coating has demonstrated versatility, scalability, and PV performance,^[6,7] and is compatible with environmentally friendly solvents.^[8,9]

Sincere efforts have been laid to fabricate CZTS as an efficient PV material, however, its development has been halted in the last years and the best-reported efficiency of 12.6 % is still far from its Shockley-Queisser limit.^[10] Limitations in CZTS performance are found in both the interfaces and intrinsic materials properties. Low charge carrier lifetime, interface barriers, and band tailing are sources of current loss,^[11-13] while band-gap fluctuation, non-ohmic contacts, grain boundaries, deep defects, band misalignment with the buffer, double layer formation, and recombination by point defects are identified as the reasons for a high voltage deficit.^[14-18] Most of the strategies to overcome these problems were focused on improvements of the absorber layer by alkali doping, alloying with isoelectronic elements, passivation of the interfaces, or controlling the microstructure.

One of the promising approaches to overcome the absorber limitations has been found in the cation substitution of Zn^{2+} by Cd^{2+} . Cd substitution leads to an absorber with enlarged grain size, reduced secondary phases, avoids Cu – Zn disorder defects, and increases minority lifetime, resulting in devices with improved PV performance and thicker depletion widths.^[19-22] The resulting alloys are compatible with wet chemistry deposition methods, however, it raises concerns about their toxicity. Metallic and Cd-based compounds have limited large-scale applications due to their high toxicity and water solubility. Though Cd is not directly abundant in the earth's crust, it can be obtained as a by-product from Zn mining, resulting in a higher supply than demand, which makes it one of the cheapest metals.^[23] A stimulating approach would be to develop applications for stable and insoluble Cd compounds with reduced toxicity, along with a lower processing cost, which can reduce Cd emission to the environment, avoiding its disposal as waste.^[24]

On the other hand, the exploitation of different PV architectures is limited rather than the standard substrate with Mo as back contact. Substrate architecture, inherited from CIGS, presents a good conductivity and stability at the required temperatures, but an uncontrolled growth of a $\text{Mo}(\text{S},\text{Se})_2$ layer remains challenging to avoid, creating a non-ohmic contact on the back surface. Moreover, this architecture is incompatible with semi-transparent or top-cell tandem applications. Alternatively, this issue can be overcome by the superstrate architecture based on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO), is thermally stable, and employ similar low-cost manufacturing with abundant elements. However, poor compatibility has been found between FTO/ TiO_2 and CZTS. Various reasons have been proposed for this poor compatibility, such as lower quality of the absorber layer, oxides formation, or high defect density in the interface.^[25,26]

In this work, we employ a sustainable (water-ethanol mixed) solvent to prepare the absorber thin films by spray pyrolysis, and we perform a cation substitution to evaluate the compatibility of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Cd}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x})\text{SnS}_4$ (CCZTS) compounds with a superstrate architecture. Moreover, all the solar cell layers were fabricated by wet-chemistry deposition methods with environmentally benign solvents to allow cost-effective manufacturing. We found that compounds with higher Cd content present a higher crystallinity and grain size, along with a low defects density. The Cd content of the absorber layer also affects the front contact by element diffusion of Zn into the CdS, forming an FTO/ TiO_2 /(Cd,Zn)S contact with a correlated Cd-Zn content to the absorber layer. These in turn lead to an increase in the power conversion efficiency (PCE) from almost negligible to a maximum of 1.9 %. In addition, we inspect the stability of the best PV cells under various conditions without any encapsulation. The PV cells are chemically and thermally stable, while the sample full cation substitution has the best stability under normal working conditions for more than 80 hours.

2. Experimental details

2.1 Solar cells fabrication

Commercial FTO (TEC-8) coated glass was used as substrate and front contact for the PV cells preparation. The FTO coated glass was subjected to a cleaning procedure consisting of a 10 minutes immersion under ultra-sonication in four different baths of 2% Hellmanex-water solution, distilled water, acetone, and isopropanol. After a fast dry with compressed air, the samples were exposed to a 15 minutes UV light to remove any organic residue.

The samples were preheated on a hotplate at 500 °C in the open air, and a solution containing titanium(IV) diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) (Merck) in ethanol (Scharlab) with a volume ratio of 1:19 was sprayed on the full area of the samples, producing a 60 nm TiO₂ compact layer. A small area of the sample will be left uncovered by the subsequent layers to be used as front contact. TiO₂ paste (18NR-T Dyesol) was dispersed in ethanol with a 125 mg/mL concentration. 50 µL of the dispersion was spin-coated at 2000 rpm on the FTO/TiO₂ substrates, followed by 30 minutes of air annealing at 500 °C on a hotplate to produce a 150 nm TiO₂ mesoporous layer.

A CdS thin film was deposited by chemical bath deposition (CBD). The samples were immersed in a deionized water bath of 370 mL at 65 °C containing 75 mg of Cadmium sulphate (98%, Alfa Aesar). Then 18.2 mL of ammonia solution (30%, Alfa Aesar) were added, followed by 20 mL water solution with 200 mg of thiourea (99%, Alfa Aesar). The bath was maintained at 65 °C under constant stirring, and the samples were extracted after 10 minutes. CdS deposited on the glass side was removed with diluted HCl.

The absorber layer was prepared by spray pyrolysis from a water-ethanol molecular solution. Firstly, stock solutions were prepared by separately dissolving Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (98%, Merck), CuCl₂, ZnCl₂, and SnCl₂·2H₂O (98%, Alfa Aesar) in ethanol with a 0.1 M

concentration, and thiourea in deionized water at 1 M concentration. The precursor solution was prepared following the next steps. First, 3.56 mL of Cu solution was slowly added to 4 mL of thiourea solution to avoid gelling. Separately, a second solution was prepared by adding 1.976 mL of mixed Cd and Zn solutions, with variable percentage, to 2.47 mL of Sn solution, along with 300 μ L of HCl (37%, Fisher) to increase the stability. Both solutions were then mixed, obtaining a clear and transparent solution, and 3.7 mL of deionized water was added to get a 1:1 mix of water-ethanol. It can be deduced from the scheme (Figure 1a), all the precursor solutions were sprayed using dry air as carrier gas on preheated samples, and clean glass substrates at the same time, on a hotplate at 340 °C in open-air. The samples were then submitted to a sulfurization process at 550 °C for 1 hour inside a close quartz tubular furnace containing 50 mg of sulphur powder (99.5%, Alfa Aesar) in an argon atmosphere.

The PV cells were completed with conductive graphite paste (GST 4500) of \sim 0.2 mm thick as back contact deposited by doctor-blade. A vinyl mask was used to define the active area, measured in Figure S1, prepared with the help of Roland GS-24 cutter. The FTO front contact area was exposed by scratching the TiO₂ protective layer and covered with Ag paint (RS Pro). Finally, all the samples were heated at 100 °C for 10 minutes on a hotplate in the air to improve the graphite and Ag conductivity.

2.2 Characterizations

Electron-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was performed with a Quantax75 equipped in a TM4000 Series scanning electron microscope (SEM). X-ray diffractograms (XRD) were measured on the final device, without the graphite back contact, with a Cubix3 system from PANalytical with a Cu anode. SEM images were recorded with a Hitachi S-3400 electron microscope at 5 kV of acceleration potential. Transmittance

spectra were recorded on the finished samples with an Agilent Cary 60 UV–Vis spectrometer.

The external quantum efficiency (EQE) was measured on a PVE300 Bentham system, consisting of a 150 W Xenon lamp and a 1/4m monochromator, in a range from 300 to 1000 nm in steps of 5 nm. Capacitance-voltage ($C-V$) measurements were performed inside a faraday box with a Biologic impedance analyser, applying steps of DC voltage between 1.5 to -1.5 V and 20 mV AC perturbation of 100 kHz. Current-voltage ($J-V$) curves were measured with a Keithley 2400 source meter. Characterization under illumination was performed with a class AAA Oriel solar simulator from Newport, calibrated to 1 Sun (AM 1.5) irradiance. For the light stability, a Motic-MLC-150C (~3000 K halogen lamp) was used as a light source. The measurements were made with a microampere-meter Keithley 6487, programmed using LabVIEW software. The program tracks the maximum power point (MPP) by the perturbation-observation method of the voltage and current, recording a measurement every second.

3. Results and discussion

We prepared, the samples with different cation content by changing the ratio of Cd and Zn in the precursor solution. The ratio of Cd/(Cd+Zn) content in the precursor solution was used to denote the samples, as $x = 0$, $x = 0.25$, $x = 0.5$, $x = 0.75$ and $x = 1$. Previously, we noted that most of the Cd from the CdS layer will be diffused into the absorber layer^[27], therefore, an extra substrate without CdS with the $x = 0$ solutions was sprayed to be used as a reference of pure $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$, denoted as CZTS. The composition of the sulfurized films was measured by EDX in both glass and prepared substrates and we measured the ratio of Zn to Cd (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. a) Scheme of the architecture of the sample, with images of the precursor solutions and the final samples, and b) Cd and Zn ratio measured by EDX from the sprayed solutions on FTO/TiO₂/CdS substrate and bare glass.

We noted a linear trend of the Cd in both substrates, suggesting that the Cd and Zn content of the precursor solution is correlated with the Cd and Zn ratio of the final film. In the case of the glass substrate, the Cd content is slightly lower than expected, which can be due to the partial loss of Cd due to evaporation either during the spray pyrolysis and/or in the sulfurization step. This loss is compensated in the case of a CdS film, where the Cd content was higher in the final composition than in the precursor solution. Even in the

case of $x = 0$, where the precursor solution had no Cd, the Cd content in the final film was 35% of the metal^{2+} content, indicating that the CdS film has an impact on the final composition of the absorber layer.

The measured compositional ratios are shown in Table S1. In this case, all the samples show a copper-deficient stoichiometry, slightly below the selected ratio of the precursor solution, likely due to the contribution of the Cd from the CdS film. The Cu-deficient ratio from 0.6 – 0.9 is typically considered as a competitive value for the performance, owing to the reduction in the formation of highly harmful CuS_x secondary phases, which causes shunts and recombination due to its high conductivity and high p -type doping. [28] On the other hand, the Sn ratio is highly different from the precursor solution to the final composition. Even if a metal^{2+} rich composition is required to get an efficient CZTS absorber, a metal^{2+} poor ratio of $(\text{Cd}+\text{Zn})/\text{Sn}$ of 0.8 was deliberately used. Due to the higher volatility of Sn compounds, a high loss of Sn is usually reported during the synthesis of CZTS thin films, especially during the precursor decomposition in wet chemistry methods. [15,29] To compensate for the Sn loss, our precursor solution contains a 25% extra Sn than the stoichiometry. A final metal^{2+} rich composition was obtained in all cases in the final layers, even in the CZTS sample without CdS, showing that this is an effective technique to control the Sn ratio. Arguably, in the samples, where a CdS layer is used, the metal^{2+} ratio is higher due to the Cd contribution from the CdS. The sulphur source used in the precursor was thiourea, in a ratio 5 times higher than the stoichiometric. During the thiourea decomposition, the excess of sulphur vaporizes, creating a local area where the formation of metal-oxide secondary phases is avoided and the formation of a sulphur rich film is favoured. [30] Sulphur rich films favour the formation of quaternary phases and, during the sulfurization step, promote better crystal growth.

The structural differences produced by the cation substitution were studied by X-ray diffractograms (Figure 2a), a gradual transition from $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ to $\text{Cu}_2\text{CdSnS}_4$ (CCTS) is observed with the increase of Cd to Zn ratio in the precursor. The [112] peak situated at 28.65° gradually shift to a lower angle until 28.13° for CCTS (Figure 2b). The shift in the angle corresponds with a crystal lattice expansion due to the larger size of Cd than Zn and expanding the cell volume from 313.5 \AA^3 to 331.4 \AA^3 (Table 1) using Bragg's law. The change of crystal symmetry from kesterite to stannite is observed in the [220] peak, where the peak starts to divide into two peaks corresponding to [220] and [204] at $x = 0.25$, which corresponds with the samples where the Cd content is higher than Zn.^[31] The structure changes with high Cd content (Figure 2c), consists of a stannite-like structure, first reported in a mineral as Cernyite,^[32] where Cd and Cu are layered, in contrast with the kesterite structure. This effect can be also noticed in the $c/2a$ value from Table 1, where lower values are associated with stannite-like structures, and values close to 1 are more characteristic of kesterite.^[33] The crystallite size is estimated using the Scherrer equation from the [112] peaks and the samples showed a similar crystallite size, except for $x = 0.75$ which gave a higher value.

While the CZTS sample shows peaks corresponding to a pure phase, in the CCZTS samples, several peaks corresponding to (Cd,Zn)S secondary phase can be also deduced. Considering the excess of metal²⁺ previously detected, these peaks reveals that part of the Cd is preserved, most likely as the original CdS layer, but forming an alloy with the Zn from the precursor solution, which gradually shifts the CdS peaks to a higher angle when the Zn content in the solution is higher. This is in agreement with reported observations of Zn accumulation at the interface after high-temperature treatment.^[34] The final (Cd,Zn)S alloy formation may play an important role in the fabricated solar cells and will impact electrical properties. A high electron density and conductivity are preferred for

this phase to act as an upright electron transport material and properties where CdS is superior to ZnS. Therefore we can expect that Cd-rich samples have improved behaviour than Cd-deficient ones.

Figure 2. a) XRD pattern of the prepared samples, where the peaks associated with CCTS are indicated with the corresponding plane (ICDD reference 04-003-8937 for CCTS and 00-026-0575 for CZTS). The peaks associated with pure CdS are indicated in the $x = 1$ sample (reference 00-041-1049), while the peaks corresponding to FTO match with the spectrum of SnO₂ in all the samples (reference 01-088-0287), b) close look to the shift of the [112] plane of CCZTS and [101] of (Cd,Zn)S, and c) representation of the atomic structure of Kesterite (CZTS) and Cernyite (CCTS).

Table 1. Materials properties derived from the XRD pattern

Sample	a (Å)	c (Å)	Cell volume (Å ³)	c/2a	Crystallite size (nm)
CZTS	5.415	10.692	313.5	0.987	36.38
x=0	5.487	10.773	324.4	0.982	38.23
x=0.25	5.519	10.720	326.6	0.971	34.78
x=0.5	5.522	10.730	327.2	0.972	35.82
x=0.75	5.536	10.733	328.9	0.969	43.97
x=1	5.566	10.699	331.4	0.961	35.82

To investigate the impact of the composition on the microstructure of the absorber layer, we recorded the top-view SEM image of the samples (Figures 3a–c and Figures S2a–c). An increase of the crystal size can be noticed for the samples with a higher Cd content, indicating that Cd facilitates the crystallization similar to substrate architecture.^[35] A larger crystal size along the horizontal direction has clear advantages. The area between grains has a high number of defects and unbound atoms, which reduces the conductivity and increases charge recombination. Moreover, the diffusion of unwanted elements is favoured in the inter-grains, which can result in faster degradation due to composition changes. The size distribution of the grains shows a progressive increase of the grain size, particularly notable in $x = 0.75$ and $x = 1$ samples, where the average grain size is close to the film thickness, and therefore there are fewer impediments and inter-grain recombination through the current flow direction.

Figure 3. SEM top and cross-sectional view of the samples a, d) $x = 0.5$, b, e) $x = 0.75$ and c, f) $x = 1$. Inset depicts the histogram distribution and average of the grain size.

A cross-sectional SEM (Figure 3d, e, f and Figure S2d, e, f) of the samples reveal the layer structure and thickness of the samples. All the samples have a compact layer formation without visible voids. The layer stack consists of a 600 – 700 nm thick FTO, a compact TiO_2 layer of 30 – 40 nm, a fine grain mesoporous layer of TiO_2 of 140 – 160 nm, and an active layer formed of bigger crystals of 300 – 500 nm thick. Since CZTS and $x = 0$ samples were prepared in the same batch, the difference in the thickness can be attributed to the lack of the CdS, suggesting the significant contribution of CdS to the absorber layer. The advantage of using a mesoporous TiO_2 layer is to improve the adhesion and to increase the contact area between the absorber and the ETL, which in combination with the high pore penetration of the CdS deposited by CBD, ensures to minimize cavities at the interface. However, CZTS sample seems to have small voids and cavities at the interface due to the CdS layer absence. Cavities are not desirable since they can block part of the current and reduce the electron-hole separation in the interface.

Figure 4. a) Transmittance spectra in the UV-Visible region of the samples, b) EQE spectra of the functional solar cells, c) band-gap calculation derived from the EQE edge, d) band-gap calculation by Tauc plot, extracted from the absorption of the samples CZTS, $x = 0$ and $x = 0.25$ and e) $x = 0.5$, $x = 0.75$ and $x = 1$, and f) band-gap comparison derived from the two methods.

The optical properties of the samples were studied by measuring transmittance in the UV-Vis region (Figure 4a). The samples show a high transmittance up to 65% in the near-IR region higher than 950 nm, while the transmittance sharply decreases for shorter wavelengths, which denotes a high absorption coefficient due to band gap absorption for all the materials, an indispensable requirement for a thin-film solar cell. Since the thickness of the absorber films was only 300 – 500 nm, the light is not completely absorbed, and mild variation in the thickness are the plausible reason for the differences in the transmittance at short wavelengths, in particular for thinner samples CZTS and $x = 0.25$. The impact of the thickness on the transmittance can be found in Figure S3. Nevertheless, the thickness of the absorber layer did not impacted the PV properties due to limitations in the electrical properties.

The solar cells were prepared by the deposition of a conductive carbon electrode on top of the device, the EQE spectra were measured to study the wavelength response (Figure 4b). We noted a significant increase in the photon-to-electron conversion across the wavelengths for the devices with a higher quantity of Cd. The CZTS samples did not have gave sufficient signal and were discarded for the electro-optical measurements. Since the light absorption was similar, the electrical properties of the absorber material and/or better compatibility with the FTO/TiO₂ front contact are the plausible reason. The shape of the EQE spectra provides insight into the interface. A small shoulder in the region below 450 nm indicates losses in the front contact due to parasitic absorption of the FTO and TiO₂ layers. A thickness optimization of these layers could increase the short-wavelength light that reaches the absorber material and thus can improve the photon to electron conversion efficiency in this region. A maximum EQE is found in all the devices in the range of 450-500 nm, followed by a progressive decay of the quantum efficiency at longer wavelengths. The decreased in absorption at longer wavelengths is not sufficient to explain the loss in efficiency, we ascribed it to the carrier diffusion length since photons absorbed deeper in the absorber layer produce electron-hole pairs that have to diffuse longer to reach the *p-n* junction where the electron-hole separation occurs.

We calculated the band gap (Figure 4c) by the linear extrapolation of the $h\nu \ln(1-EQE)^2$. For comparison, the band gap of the different absorbers is extracted from the Tauc plot (Figures 4d and 4e). The calculated results (Figure 4f), showed a maximum difference between both values of 0.023 eV. A value of 1.5 eV was obtained for the pure CZTS sample, while all the other samples with Cd in the composition showed a reduction in the band gap, with a minimum value obtained of 1.41 eV for the $x = 1$ sample. However, the band gap values for this family of compounds are among the ideal values considering the Shockley-Queisser limit.

The electrical properties of the sample were studied by capacitance-voltage measurements, from where the Mott-Schottky plot was calculated (Figure S4) and the built-in potential of the junction is calculated (Figure 5). The built-in potential indicates the voltage produced at the *p-n* interface, setting an upper limit for the voltage that can be extracted. Interestingly, intermediate values of Cd-Zn in the composition result in lower built-in potential, while this value increases for pure Zn sample CZTS and high values of Cd. However, this value alone needs to be complemented with other junction properties to have a comprehensive model.

Assuming the capacitor model of the *p-n* junction, the depletion width is inversely proportional to the capacitance, following the equation $W = \epsilon \epsilon_0 \frac{A}{C}$, where W is the depletion width, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the absorber, ϵ_0 is the vacuum dielectric constant, A is the cell area and C is the capacitance. The depletion width, and therefore the capacitance, can be modified if an external voltage is applied and, at the same time, the density of free carriers N_D in the absorber layer can be calculated with the equation

$$N_D = -\frac{C^3}{q\epsilon\epsilon_0 A^2} \left(\frac{dC}{dV}\right)^{-1}. \text{ The results and values at 0 V are represented in Figure 5.}$$

A progressive increase of the depletion width and a reduction of N_D with the increase of Cd can be deduced, which correlates with the values of the EQE. This reveals that the main current limitation for the samples with a low Cd ratio is a small depletion width, drastically reducing the electron-hole pair collection, along with a high density of carriers, associated with defects that decrease the diffusion length. A high Cd ratio is found to overcome this limitation, while increasing the built-in potential, resulting in a higher charge collection with a higher potential separation.

Figure 5. Carrier density profile calculated from the C - V measurements, with the values of built-in potential, depletion width, and carrier density at short circuit condition.

The dark I - V curve was measured (Figure 6a) and all the samples present a rectification shape, with no leakage under reverse current. The samples with a higher Cd ratio present an increase of the turn-on voltage, which suggests the existence of a barrier affecting the output voltage is low in Cd samples since the built-in potential follows a different trend. These barriers are likely produced at the p - n interface due to band bending, caused by a high charge density in the p -type absorber. In addition, barriers can be also produced in the grain boundaries of the polycrystalline absorber, thus the samples with higher crystallinity can mitigate this problem.

The characteristic J - V curve under 1 Sun (AM 1.5) illumination is represented in Figure 6b, and the statistical distribution of the PV properties, over 10 individual devices for each condition (except for the CZTS sample due to low values), is shown in Figures 6c – 6f. The open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) has an increasing trend for the samples with higher Cd content, especially for the samples $x = 0.75$ and $x = 1$, where it reaches a value of 540

mV, while the best value of sample $x = 0.5$ is just 402 mV. This increment seems to be highly correlated with the increase in the built-in potential, which allows an efficient charge separation, and the reduction of defects density, reducing the traps states and recombination, allowing the separated charges to retain a higher potential. The remaining (Cd,Zn)S as secondary phase found in the XRD plays an important role in the V_{oc} increment. CdS are well-known buffer material, with low resistance and high n -type doping, while ZnS usually present high resistance and low n -type doping, produce barriers that make charge separation difficult. However, it has been reported that (Cd,Zn)S can reduce the interface recombination and produce solar cells with better performance.^[36,37] The short circuit current (J_{sc}) values naturally follow a similar trend as in the EQE and the thickness of the depletion width. In this case, sample $x = 0.75$ stands out with better values, followed by the $x = 1$ sample. High Cd content improves the charge collection, however, the short-circuit current values are still below the ideal values that can be attained with these materials (up to 34 mA/cm^2 for a 1.4 eV band-gap according to the Shockley-Queisser limit). The low fill factor is of concern (between 25 and 30 % in most cases), indicating the existence of parasitic resistances, most likely due to non-optimized front and back contacts.

Figure 6. a) Dark $J-V$ curves, b) $J-V$ curves of the efficient device of each condition under 1 Sun illumination, c) V_{OC} , d) J_{SC} , e) FF, and f) PCE statistical (boxes) and values (red dots) extracted from the $J-V$ curves under 1 Sun illumination.

Comparing devices with the same composition, but with different absorber thicknesses, (Figure S5), we noted a change in the initial PV performance. Moreover, a reduction of the PV parameters for the absorber thicker than 500 nm corroborates a strong limitation existing in the diffusion length and conductivity within the bulk material.

Taking into account, the overall power conversion efficiency (PCE) is found to have a clear improvement for the device with the higher Cd content, with a remarkable record value of 1.9 % for $x = 0.75$ and 1.4 % for $x = 1$. Considering that is the first time, under our knowledge, that CCTS is reported to be used in a superstrate architecture, these PCE values are promising. Moreover, the results gave good reproducibility, with a maximum dispersion of 30% among different samples.

While the PCE extracted from the $J-V$ curve is the standard parameter to compare with other PV technologies, it is not an important parameter to evaluate the potential of a PV technology to substitute the current PV technologies. Reliability is a critical factor when a new PV technology has to compete with established technologies. Thus, we have focussed on the three main stability aspects: chemical, thermal, and light stability. In the context of chemical stability, we noted that the samples have low or unnoticeable changes when exposed to common solvents (water, acetone, isopropanol, and ethanol), or even highly basic and acid environments, such as NH_3 vapours typically used in the CBD process, or concentrated HCl, in agreement with other reports for this type of solar cells.^[38] The high chemical stability will not only be beneficial to keep a constant PCE over time but also to ensure that the potentially dangerous elements such as Cd are not released to the environment.

We then investigated thermal stability by applying a heat treatment to the samples of 150 °C for 10 minutes on a hot plate, (Figure S5). The device PV parameters decrease after heat treatment, which affects mainly the V_{OC} and J_{SC} . However, after keeping the samples under dark for two weeks, all the PV parameters recovered to their original values. This temporal behaviour suggests that the effect of the temperature in these samples is not due to chemical reactions, such as oxidation or decomposition, but rather a trap state

activation in the p - n junction. Proper control of the trap states, by an appropriate dopant, for example, can mitigate this and increase the temperature stability.

Figure 7. a) PCE evolution under continuous illumination for the sample, $x = 0.75$, and c) $x = 1$, b) values of voltage and current measured at the tracked maximum power point for the sample $x = 0.75$, and d) for $x = 1$.

Subsequently, the light stability was probed by monitoring the maximum power point (MPP) under continuous illumination for several hours, (Figure 7). Since the illumination was provided with a halogen lamp, the intensity was calibrated with reference cells, by adjusting the initial J_{SC} to the value measured under one Sun. The comparison of the J - V curves at one Sun (Figure S6) was made and by doing this, we mimic the samples close to a real application scenario. We compared the conditions, of $x = 0.75$ and $x = 1$, and noted different behaviours. The sample $x = 0.75$ has a decreasing trend of the MPP voltage during the first 5 hours, followed by a drop of the voltage that elevates the current. This

behaviour could be caused by the creation of shunt paths due to micro dielectric breakdowns. At this point, the voltage is almost kept constant, while the photo-current shows a decrement until and is stabilised after 40 hours. As previously seen, the short-circuit current was mostly dependent on the depletion width, which suggests that this current reduction is caused by the slow activation of traps that increases the density of free carriers in the absorber, reducing the depletion width and therefore the collected charges. For the sample $x = 1$, we found a progressive increase of the MPP during the first 20 hours, and then, a stabilized behaviour in the investigated window of 60 hours. The difference between the samples indicates that the small quantity of Zn in the sample $x = 0.75$ has an impact on light stability. CdS are known to exhibit high photoconductivity under visible illumination,^[39] lowering the resistance and improving its properties as a buffer layer, which causes an increase of the PCE. However, this effect is much lower or even disappears, in a (Cd,Zn)S solid solution,^[40] explaining why only the $x = 1$ sample, that contains pure CdS, presents an increase of the PCE under continuous illumination. These findings postulate CCTS as an attractive absorber material for the development of a new generation of stable, thin-film, and cost-effective PV technology based on a superstrate architecture, while CCZTS could be also a candidate if the light stability issues can be addressed. We identified the limiting factors that can be addressed to improve the PCE. The main limitation was found in the charge collection, affecting the short-circuit current. A charge collection dependence on the depletion width instead of the absorber thickness indicates that the limitation comes from a low diffusion length of the photo-generated electron-hole pairs. Strategies such as doping, alloying, or nanostructures can address such limitations. Additionally, optimization of both the front and back contacts could reduce the series resistance and improve the FF.

4. Conclusions

Water-ethanol spray pyrolysis deposition was used as a benign media to prepare $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Cd,Zn})\text{SnS}_4$ films to be used as absorber material in all-solution-processed superstrate-type solar cells. The Zn-Cd ratio impacts the electro-optical properties. A high Cd content improves the crystal growth and avoids the formation of (Cd,Zn)S as secondary phases, largely increasing the depletion width of the *p-n* junction and thus photo-generated charge collection. Both the V_{OC} and J_{SC} increase significantly, leading to PCE values from 0.3 % for low Cd content to 1.9 % for higher ones. The fabricated solar cells also showed chemical, thermal and light stability, suggesting large-scale applications. The main limitations are found to be a low exciton diffusion, impeding a complete charge collection, and the low FF. Overcoming these limitations could promote this type of solar cell as a green and cost-effective alternative to the current PV technologies and, concurrently, avoid the use of critical or scarce elements.

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